

The Merrifield-Simmons Indices of Triangle-Trees with k Pendant-Triangles

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Abstract: Triangle-trees are a kind of graphs derived from Koch networks. The Merrifield-Simmons index of a graph is the total number of the independent sets of the graph. We prove that $P_{k,n-k}^\Delta$ is the triangle-tree with maximal Merrifield-Simmons index among all the triangle-trees with n triangles and k pendant triangles.

Key Words: Triangle-tree; Merrifield-Simmons index; pendant-triangle.

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§1. Introduction

The Koch networks (see [10], [13]) are derived from the Koch fractals (see [4], [9]) and are constructed iteratively. Let $K_{m,g}$ (m is a natural number) denote the Koch network after g iterations. Then, the family of Koch networks can be generated in the following way: initially ($g = 0$), $K_{m,0}$ consists of a triangle with three nodes labeled respectively by x, y, z , which have the highest degree among all nodes in the networks. For $g \geq 1$, $K_{m,g}$ is obtained from $K_{m,g-1}$ by performing the following operation. For each of the three nodes in every existing triangle in $K_{m,g-1}$, we add m groups of nodes. Each node group contains two nodes, both of which and their 'mother' node are connected to one another forming a new triangle. In other words, to get $K_{m,g}$ from $K_{m,g-1}$, we can replace each triangle in $K_{m,g-1}$ by a connected cluster on the right-hand side of the arrow in Fig.1.

Note that a Koch network does not have any cycle except for the triangles, we can call such a graph a triangle-tree.

Definition 1.1 Let T_n^Δ (n is a natural number) denote a triangle-tree with n triangles. The family of triangle-trees can be generated in the following way: initially $n = 1$, T_1^Δ consists of a triangle with three vertices labeled respectively by x, y, z . For $n \geq 2$, T_n^Δ is obtained from T_{n-1}^Δ by adding a pair of new vertices u, v , both of them are joined to a vertex of T_{n-1}^Δ and the edge uv is also added to form a new triangle. In other words, to get T_n^Δ from T_{n-1}^Δ , we add a new triangle to T_{n-1}^Δ by identifying a vertex of the new triangle with a vertex of T_{n-1}^Δ .

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Fig.1

Fig.2

Obviously Koch networks are all triangle-trees. Suppose T^Δ is a triangle-tree, Δ is a triangle of T , if there are two vertices with degree two in Δ , we call the triangle Δ a pendant triangle of T^Δ . The triangle-path P_n^Δ (see Fig.2) is the only triangle-tree with only two pendant triangles and the triangle-star S_n^Δ (see Fig.2) is the only triangle-tree with n pendant triangles. For any two triangles Δ_1 and Δ_2 of T^Δ , if Δ_1 and Δ_2 have a common vertex, we say Δ_1 and Δ_2 are adjacent, and the distance between Δ_1 and Δ_2 is 1, denoted by $d(\Delta_1, \Delta_2) = 1$. If Δ_1 and Δ_2 do not have a common vertex, there is only one triangle-path between them. If the triangle-path between Δ_1 and Δ_2 contains d triangles, we say the distance between Δ_1 and Δ_2 is $d - 1$, denoted by $d(\Delta_1, \Delta_2) = d - 1$. The diameter of a triangle-tree is denoted by d^Δ , defined as

$$d^\Delta(T_n^\Delta) = \max\{d(\Delta, \Delta') \mid \Delta, \Delta' \text{ are two triangles of } T_n^\Delta\}.$$

Throughout this paper $G = (V, E)$ is a finite simple undirected graph with vertex set $V = V(G)$ and edge set $E = E(G)$. The neighborhood of a vertex $v \in V$ is the set $N_G(v) = \{w : w \in V, vw \in E\}$, $d_G(v) = |N_G(v)|$, and $N_G[v] = N_G(v) \cup \{v\}$. For $S \subseteq V$, we use $G - S$ for the subgraph induced by $V(G) \setminus S$, $G[S]$ for the subgraph of G induced by S and $N_S(v) = \{w : w \in S, vw \in E(G)\}$. For $F \subseteq E(G)$, we use $G - F$ for the subgraph of G obtained by deleting F .

Let G be a graph on n vertices. Two vertices of G are said to be independent if they are not adjacent in G . A k -independent set of G is a set of k -mutually independent vertices. Denote by $f_k(G)$ the number of the k -independent sets of G . For convenience, we regard the

empty vertex set as an independent set. Then $f_0(G) = 1$ for any graph G . Let $\alpha(G)$ denote the cardinality of a maximal independent set of G .

The *Merrifield-Simmons index* was introduced by Prodinger and Tichy in 1982, which is defined by

$$i(G) = \sum_{s=0}^{\alpha(G)} f_s(G),$$

although it is called Fibonacci number of a graph in [8]. It is one of the most popular topological indices in chemistry, which was extensively studied in monograph [7]. Now there have been many papers studying the Merrifield-Simmons index. In [8], Prodinger and Tichy showed that, for trees with order n , the star has the maximal Merrifield-Simmons index and the path has the minimal Merrifield-Simmons index. In [6], Li et al characterized the tree with the maximal Merrifield-Simmons index among the trees with given diameter. In [11], Yu and Lv characterized the trees with maximal Merrifield-Simmons indices, among the trees with given pendant vertices. For more results on Merrifield-Simmons index, see [1-3], [5] and [12].

Due to the similarity of triangle-trees and ordinary trees, it is very interesting to study the Merrifield-Simmons indices of triangle-trees. It is easy verify that, among all the triangle-trees with n triangles, S_n^Δ is the triangle-tree with maximal Merrifield-Simmons index and P_n^Δ is the triangle-tree with minimal Merrifield-Simmons index. As noting this result is similar to the result of ordinary trees, we consider all the triangle-trees with n triangles and k pendant triangles. It is very interesting to find that $P_{k,n-k}^\Delta$ (as shown in Fig. 3) is the triangle-tree with maximal Merrifield-Simmons index among all such triangle-trees, and this result is also similar to the result of ordinary trees.

Fig.3

§2. Lemmas and Results

We first introduce the following lemma, which is obvious and well-known.

Lemma 2.1 For a graph G , we have

- (1) $i(G) = i(G - v) + i(G - N[v])$ for any $v \in V(G)$;
- (2) $i(G) = i(G - e) + i(G - N[e])$ for any $e \in E(G)$;
- (3) If $G = G_1 \cup G_2$, then $i(G) = i(G_1)i(G_2)$.

Using the above lemma, we can derive some recursion formulas on the Merrifield-Simmons

index of the triangle-path P_n^Δ . Denote $a_n = i(P_n^\Delta)$. It is easy to see that $a_1 = 4, a_2 = 10, a_3 = 24$. Let $Q_n = P_n^\Delta - v_1$, where v_1 is one of the vertices with degree two of the pendant-triangle of P_n^Δ (as shown in Fig 2) and $b_n = i(Q_n)$. It is easy to see that $b_1 = 3, b_2 = 7, b_3 = 17$. Let $R_n = Q_n - v_{2n+1}$, where v_{2n+1} is one of the vertices with degree two of another pendant-triangle of P_n^Δ (as shown in Fig.2). It is easy to see that $c_1 = 2, c_2 = 5, c_3 = 12$.

By Lemma 2.1, we know

$$\begin{aligned} a_n &= b_n + b_{n-1}, \\ b_n &= a_{n-1} + b_{n-1} = c_n + c_{n-1}, \\ c_n &= b_{n-1} + c_{n-1}. \end{aligned}$$

So we have

$$\begin{aligned} b_{n+1} &= 2b_n + b_{n-1}, \\ a_{n+1} &= 2a_n + a_{n-1}, \\ c_{n+1} &= 2c_n + c_{n-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Let $P_k^\Delta = \Delta_1\Delta_2\cdots\Delta_k$ be a path of a triangle-tree T^Δ , where $\Delta_i = v_{2i-1}v_{2i}v_{2i+1}$. If $d_{T^\Delta}(v_1) \geq 6, d_{T^\Delta}(v_{2k+1}) \geq 6, d_{T^\Delta}(v_{2i}) = 2 (1 \leq i \leq k)$ and $d_{T^\Delta}(v_{2i+1}) = 4 (1 \leq i \leq k-1)$, we call P_k^Δ an internal triangle-path of T^Δ . If the triangle $\Delta_1 = v_1v_2v_3$ is a pendant triangle of $T^\Delta, d_{T^\Delta}(v_{2k+1}) \geq 6, d_{T^\Delta}(v_{2i}) = 2 (1 \leq i \leq k)$ and $d_{T^\Delta}(v_{2i+1}) = 4 (1 \leq i \leq k-1)$, we call P^Δ a pendant triangle-path of T^Δ . Let $s(T^\Delta)$ be the number of vertices in T^Δ with degree not less than 6 and $p(T^\Delta)$ be the number of pendant triangle-paths in T^Δ with length not less than 1.

Fig.4

Denote $\mathcal{T}_{n,k}^\Delta (3 \leq k \leq n-1)$ be the set of all triangle-trees with n triangles and k pendant

triangles. In the following, we shall define two kinds of operations of $T^\Delta \in \mathcal{T}_{n,k}^\Delta$ and show that these two kinds of operations make the Merrifield-Simmons indices of the triangle-tree increase strictly.

If $T^\Delta \in \mathcal{T}_{n,k}^\Delta$, $T^\Delta \not\cong P_{k,n-k}^\Delta$ and $p(T^\Delta) \neq 0$, then T^Δ can be seen as the triangle-trees T_1^Δ or T_2^Δ as shown in Fig.4, where $\Delta_1\Delta_2 \cdots \Delta_s$ ($s \geq 2$) is a pendant path of T^Δ with s triangles, G_1 and G_2 are two subtriangle-trees of T^Δ and $|V(G_1)| \geq 3$, $|V(G_2)| \geq 3$. If T_0^Δ is obtained from T_1^Δ or T_2^Δ by Operation I (as shown in Fig.4), it is easy to see that $T_0^\Delta \in \mathcal{T}_{n,k}^\Delta$.

Now we show that operation I makes the Merrifield-Simmons indices of the triangle-trees increase strictly.

Lemma 2.2 *If T_0^Δ is obtained from T_1^Δ or T_2^Δ by operation I, then $i(T_0^\Delta) > i(T_1^\Delta)$ and $i(T_0^\Delta) > i(T_2^\Delta)$.*

Proof Let $N_{G_1}[v] = V_1$, $N_{G_2}[u] = V_2$ in T_1^Δ , $N_{G_2}[u'] = V_2'$ in T_2^Δ and $N_{G_2}[w] = V_3$ in T_0^Δ .

If $s \geq 3$, by Lemma 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} i(T_1^\Delta) &= i(T_1^\Delta - v) + i(T_1^\Delta - N_{T_1^\Delta}[v]) \\ &= i(G_1 - v)(2i(G_2 - u)b_s + i(G_2 - V_2)b_{s-1}) + i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - u)b_s, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i(T_2^\Delta) &= i(T_2^\Delta - v) + i(T_2^\Delta - N_{T_2^\Delta}[v]) \\ &= i(G_1 - v)(i(G_2 - u')a_s + i(G_2 - V_2')b_s) + i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - u')b_s, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i(T_0^\Delta) &= i(T_0^\Delta - v) + i(T_0^\Delta - N_{T_0^\Delta}[v]) \\ &= i(G_1 - v)(3i(G_2 - w)c_s + i(G_2 - V_3)c_{s-1}) \\ &\quad + i(G_1 - V_1)(3i(G_2 - w)c_{s-1} + i(G_2 - V_3)c_{s-2}). \end{aligned}$$

Obviously, $i(G_2 - w) = i(G_2 - u') = i(G_2 - u)$ and $i(G_2 - V_3) = i(G_2 - V_2') = i(G_2 - V_2)$, so we have

$$\begin{aligned} &i(T_0^\Delta) - i(T_1^\Delta) \\ &= i(G_1 - v)i(G_2 - u)(3c_s - 2b_s) + i(G_1 - v)i(G_2 - V_2)(c_{s-1} - b_{s-1}) \\ &\quad + i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - u)(3c_{s-1} - b_s) + i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - V_2)c_{s-2} \\ &= i(G_1 - v)i(G_2 - u)c_{s-2} - i(G_1 - v)i(G_2 - V_2)c_{s-2} \\ &\quad - i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - u)c_{s-2} + i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - V_2)c_{s-2} \\ &= c_{s-2}(i(G_1 - v) - i(G_1 - V_1))(i(G_2 - u) - i(G_2 - V_2)). \end{aligned}$$

Since $s \geq 3$, $c_{s-2} > 0$, $i(G_1 - v) - i(G_1 - V_1) > 0$ and $i(G_2 - u) - i(G_2 - V_2) > 0$, we know $i(T_0^\Delta) - i(T_1^\Delta) > 0$ when $s \geq 3$.

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned}
& i(T_0^\Delta) - i(T_2^\Delta) \\
&= i(G_1 - v)i(G_2 - u')(3c_s - a_s) + i(G_1 - v)i(G_2 - V_2')(c_{s-1} - b_s) \\
&\quad + i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - u')(3c_{s-1} - b_s) + i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - V_2')c_{s-2} \\
&= i(G_1 - v)i(G_2 - u')(c_{s-2} + 2c_{s-1}) + i(G_1 - v)i(G_2 - V_2')(-c_{s-2} - 2c_{s-1}) \\
&\quad + i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - u')(-c_{s-2}) + i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - V_2')c_{s-2} \\
&= c_{s-2}(i(G_1 - v) - i(G_1 - V_1))(i(G_2 - u') - i(G_2 - V_2')) \\
&\quad + 2c_{s-1}i(G_1 - v)(i(G_2 - u') - i(G_2 - V_2')) > 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $i(T_0^\Delta) - i(T_2^\Delta) > 0$ when $s \geq 3$. If $s = 2$, similarly, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& i(T_0^\Delta) - i(T_1^\Delta) \\
&= i(G_1 - v)i(G_2 - u)(3c_2 - 2b_2) + i(G_1 - v)i(G_2 - V_2)(c_1 - b_1) \\
&\quad + i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - u)(3c_1 - b_2) + i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - V_2) \\
&= (i(G_1 - v) - i(G_1 - V_1))(i(G_2 - u) - i(G_2 - V_2)).
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& i(T_0^\Delta) - i(T_2^\Delta) \\
&= i(G_1 - v)i(G_2 - u')(3c_2 - a_2) + i(G_1 - v)i(G_2 - V_2')(c_1 - b_2) \\
&\quad + i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - u')(3c_1 - b_2) + i(G_1 - V_1)i(G_2 - V_2') \\
&= (i(G_1 - v) - i(G_1 - V_1))(i(G_2 - u') - i(G_2 - V_2')) \\
&\quad + 4i(G_1 - v)(i(G_2 - u') - i(G_2 - V_2')) > 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $i(T_0^\Delta) - i(T_1^\Delta) > 0$ and $i(T_0^\Delta) - i(T_2^\Delta) > 0$ when $s = 2$. \square

From Lemma 2.2, we can immediately get the following result.

Lemma 2.3 *Let $T^\Delta \in \mathcal{T}_{n,k}^\Delta$ ($3 \leq k \leq n - 1$), $T^\Delta \not\cong P_{k,n-k}^\Delta$ and $p(T^\Delta) \geq 1$.*

(1) *If $s(T^\Delta) = 1$, we can finally get a triangle-tree T'^Δ by operation I with $i(T'^\Delta) > i(T^\Delta)$, and $p(T'^\Delta) = 1$; it is easy to see that $T'^\Delta \cong P_{k,n-k}^\Delta$;*

(2) *If $s(T^\Delta) > 1$, we can finally get a triangle-tree T'^Δ by operation I with $i(T'^\Delta) > i(T^\Delta)$ and $p(T'^\Delta) = 0$.*

If $T^\Delta \in \mathcal{T}_{n,k}^\Delta$ ($3 \leq k \leq n - 1$), $T^\Delta \not\cong P_{n,k}^\Delta$ and $p(T^\Delta) = 0$, then we can find two pendant triangles Δ_1 and Δ'_1 of T^Δ such that $d(\Delta_1, \Delta'_1) = d^\Delta(T^\Delta)$. Suppose $\Delta_1 = uu_1u'_1$ and $\Delta'_1 = vv_1v'_1$, where u_1, u'_1, v_1, v'_1 are the vertices with degree 2 and $d(u) \geq 6$, $d(v) \geq 6$. Then the triangle-tree can be seen as the triangle-tree T^Δ shown in Fig 5, where $\Delta_1, \Delta_2, \dots, \Delta_s$ are pendant triangles with common vertex u , $\Delta'_1, \Delta'_2, \dots, \Delta'_t$ are pendant triangles with common vertex v , G_1 is the subgraph of T^Δ induced by $V(T^\Delta) \setminus \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^s V(\Delta_i) \cup \bigcup_{i=1}^t V(\Delta'_i) \right)$.

Fig.5

Note that if $d(\Delta_1, \Delta_2) = 3$, then $x = y$; if $d(\Delta_1, \Delta_2) \geq 4$, then $|V(G_1)| \geq 5$. T'^Δ is a triangle-tree got from T^Δ by moving the pendant triangles $\Delta'_2, \Delta'_3, \dots, \Delta'_t$ from v to u , and T''^Δ is a triangle-tree got from T^Δ by moving the pendant triangles $\Delta_2, \Delta_3, \dots, \Delta_s$ from u to v . We say both of T'^Δ and T''^Δ are obtained from T^Δ by Operation II. It is easy to see that $T'^\Delta, T''^\Delta \in \Gamma_{n,k}^\Delta$, $p(T'^\Delta) = p(T''^\Delta) = 1$ and $s(T'^\Delta) = s(T''^\Delta) = s(T^\Delta) - 1$.

Lemma 2.4 *If T'^Δ and T''^Δ are obtained from T^Δ by Operation II, then either $i(T'^\Delta) > i(T^\Delta)$ or $i(T''^\Delta) > i(T^\Delta)$.*

Proof If $d(\Delta_1, \Delta'_1) \geq 3$, then $N_{G_1}(u) = \{x, x'\}$ and $N_{G_1}(v) = \{y, y'\}$. Note that if $d(\Delta_1, \Delta'_1) = 3$, then $x = y$. By Lemma 2.2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} i(T^\Delta) &= i(T^\Delta - u) + i(T^\Delta - N_{T^\Delta}[u]) \\ &= 3^s(3^t i(G_1) + i(G_1 - \{y, y'\})) + 3^t i(G_1 - \{x, x'\}) + i(G_1 - \{x, x', y, y'\}), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i(T'^\Delta) &= i(T'^\Delta - u) + i(T'^\Delta - N_{T'^\Delta}[u]) \\ &= 3^{s+t-1}(3i(G_1) + i(G_1 - \{y, y'\})) + 3i(G_1 - \{x, x'\}) + i(G_1 - \{x, x', y, y'\}), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i(T''^\Delta) &= i(T''^\Delta - u) + i(T''^\Delta - N_{T''^\Delta}[u]) \\ &= 3(3^{s+t-1} i(G_1) + i(G_1 - \{y, y'\})) + 3^{s+t-1} i(G_1 - \{x, x'\}) + i(G_1 - \{x, x', y, y'\}). \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to see that

$$i(T'^\Delta) - i(T^\Delta) = 3(3^{t-1} - 1)(3^{s-1} i(G_1 - \{y, y'\}) - i(G_1 - \{x, x'\})),$$

$$i(T''^\Delta) - i(T^\Delta) = 3(3^{s-1} - 1)(3^{t-1}i(G_1 - \{x, x'\}) - i(G_1 - \{y, y'\})).$$

Note that $s, t \geq 2$. If $i(T'^\Delta) - i(T^\Delta) \leq 0$, we have $3^{s-1}i(G_1 - \{y, y'\}) \leq i(G_1 - \{x, x'\})$. Then we have

$$i(T''^\Delta) - i(T^\Delta) \geq 3(3^{s-1} - 1)(3^{s-1}3^{t-1} - 1)i(G_1 - \{y, y'\}) > 0.$$

If $d(\Delta_1, \Delta'_1) = 2$, we have $T'^\Delta \cong T''^\Delta$. Suppose $N_{G_2}(u) = \{v, w\}$, $N_{G_2}(v) = \{u, w\}$, then

$$i(T'^\Delta) - i(T^\Delta) = 3(3^{t-1} - 1)(3^{s-1} - 1)i(G_1 - w) > 0.$$

Therefore, if T'^Δ and T''^Δ are obtained from T^Δ by operation II, then either $i(T'^\Delta) > i(T^\Delta)$ or $i(T''^\Delta) > i(T^\Delta)$. \square

Theorem 2.5 *Let $T^\Delta \in \mathcal{T}_{n,k}^\Delta$. Then $i(T^\Delta) \leq 3^{k-1}b_{n-k+1} + b_{n-k}$, the equality holds if and only if $T^\Delta \cong P_{k,n-k}^\Delta$.*

Proof By Lemma 2.1, it is easy to see that

$$i(P_{k,n-k}^\Delta) = 3^{k-1}b_{n-k+1} + b_{n-k}.$$

Since $\mathcal{T}_{n,2}^\Delta = \{P_n^\Delta\}$ and $P_n^\Delta \cong P_{n,0}^\Delta$, $\mathcal{T}_{n,n}^\Delta = \{S_n^\Delta\}$ and $S_n^\Delta \cong P_{2,n-2}^\Delta$, we may assume $3 \leq k \leq n-1$. It is sufficient to show that $i(T^\Delta) < i(P_{k,n-k}^\Delta)$ for any $T^\Delta \in \mathcal{T}_{n,k}^\Delta$ and $T^\Delta \not\cong P_{k,n-k}^\Delta$.

For $T^\Delta \in \mathcal{T}_{n,k}^\Delta$ ($3 \leq k \leq n-1$) and $T^\Delta \not\cong P_{k,n-k}^\Delta$, we know $1 \leq s(T^\Delta) \leq n-k$, we shall show $i(T^\Delta) \leq i(P_{k,n-k}^\Delta)$ by induction on $s(T^\Delta)$. When $s(T^\Delta) = 1$, since $T^\Delta \not\cong P_{k,n-k}^\Delta$, we have $p(T^\Delta) \geq 2$. By (1) of Lemma 2.3, we have $i(T^\Delta) < i(P_{k,n-k}^\Delta)$. Suppose the result holds for any triangle-tree T'^Δ with $s(T'^\Delta) = s-1$. Let $s(T^\Delta) = s \geq 2$. If $p(T^\Delta) \neq 0$, by (2) of Lemma 2.3, we can get a triangle-tree $T_1^\Delta \in \mathcal{T}_{n,k}^\Delta$ such that $p(T_1^\Delta) = 0$, $s(T_1^\Delta) = s$ and $i(T_1^\Delta) > i(T^\Delta)$. Then by Lemma 2.4, we can get a triangle-tree $T_2^\Delta \in \mathcal{T}_{n,k}^\Delta$ from T_1^Δ such that $p(T_2^\Delta) = 1$, $s(T_2^\Delta) = s-1$ and $i(T_2^\Delta) > i(T_1^\Delta)$. By the induction hypothesis, we have

$$i(T^\Delta) < i(T_1^\Delta) < i(T_2^\Delta) < i(P_{k,n-k}^\Delta).$$

Therefore, if $T^\Delta \in \mathcal{T}_{n,k}^\Delta$, then $i(T^\Delta) \leq 3^{k-1}b_{n-k+1} + b_{n-k} = i(P_{k,n-k}^\Delta)$ and the equality holds if and only if $T^\Delta \cong P_{k,n-k}^\Delta$. \square

Lemma 2.6 *For $3 \leq k \leq n$, $i(P_{n-k+2,k-2}^\Delta) > i(P_{n-k+3,k-3}^\Delta)$.*

Proof By Lemma 2.1, it is easy to see that

$$i(P_{n-k+2,k-2}^\Delta) = 3^{k-1}b_{n-k+1} + b_{n-k},$$

$$i(P_{n-k+3,k-3}^\Delta) = 3^{k-2}b_{n-k+2} + b_{n-k+1}.$$

Since $b_{n+1} = 2b_n + b_{n-1}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} i(P_{k,n-k}^\Delta) - i(P_{n-k+3,k-3}^\Delta) &= 3^{k-1}b_{n-k+1} + b_{n-k} - 3^{k-2}b_{n-k+2} + b_{n-k+1} \\ &= (3^{k-2} - 1)(b_{n-k+1} - b_{n-k}) > 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $i(P_{n-k+2,k-2}^\Delta) > i(P_{n-k+3,k-3}^\Delta)$ for $3 \leq k \leq n$. \square

From Theorem 2.5 and Lemma 2.6, we can immediately get the following result.

Corollary 2.7 *Let T^Δ be a triangle-tree with $2n + 1$ vertices and n triangles. Then*

- (1) $i(T^\Delta) \leq 3^n + 1$ and the equality holds if and only if $T^\Delta \cong S_n^\Delta$;
- (2) If $T^\Delta \not\cong S_n^\Delta$, then $i(T^\Delta) \leq 7 \times 3^{n-2} + 3$ and the equality holds if and only if $T^\Delta \cong P_{3,n-3}^\Delta$.

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